

Christ Apostolic Church

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The church, Christ Apostolic Church is reputed to be the first Pentecostal church to have emerged from the shore of Nigeria. The church was started through the effort of individuals who desire apostolic power and reawakening of the church like the biblical apostolic age. Prominent among the pioneers of the church are Oba/Pastor Isaac Akinyele, Pastor David Ogunleye Odubanjo, Joseph Sadare, Miss Sophia Odunlami and Evangelist Joseph Ayo Babalola. These men and women were part of the individuals who laid the foundation of what is today known as Christ Apostolic Church. Beginning from the Church missionary society of Our Saviours' Anglican church in Ijebu Ode in 1918, a group of people formed a prayer society called "Egbe Aladura" meaning prayer society/group. This prayer society/group spearheaded by Joseph B. Sadare was forced to move out of the Anglican church as her practices were considered antithetical to the doctrine of Anglican church. In the year 1930, there was an outbreak of revival through Evangelist Joseph Ayo Babalola in Oke Oye Ilesha. This revival signaled a new era for the group as large number of people joined them as members. As this revival attracted a large number of people to the group, it also attracted persecution for them from the mission church and government. However, the group kept waxing strong in all fronts. The group through the effort of Pastor DO Odubanjo was affiliated to the Faith Tabernacle of America. The relationship was soon severe with the Faith tabernacle of the America as a result of irreconcilable differences that broke up among the leaders of the church in America. The group sought for alliance with the British Apostolic Church in Bradford. On 23rd September 1931, three missionaries who were representatives of the British church arrived in Nigeria. In November 1931 first seven leaders of the group were ordained as the Pastor of the church. The church was formally incorporated and registered by the government as Christ Apostolic Church in the year 1943. It was the first indigenous church to be registered in Nigeria. The church believes in the power of prayer, holiness living, divine healing, all sufficient God who is able to provide without going into debt or borrowing. The church also involve in regular bible study, prayer meetings, keeping prayer vigil and tarrying meeting for the Holy Spirit. The church CAC as at today is a popular Pentecostal church in Nigeria. It has since developed from a parlour state to be one of the widespread denominational churches in Nigeria. Beyond this, the church has different department like Good women, Youth department, Royal Shepherd, Christ Apostolic Church Men Association (CACMA). Also the church has many educational institutions which are run by the church. Theological seminary where Church workers are being trained, Private University known as Joseph Ayo Babalola University in Nigeria. The church also runs a satellite television station known as CACTV. As at today, the church has denominational churches in other Africa countries, America and Europe..

Date Range: 1918 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: J.A. Ademakinwa(1971) Itan ijo Aposteli Kristi (translated 2012)History of Christ Apostolic Church , The Faith of Our Fathers, (Lagos: The battlecry Christian Ministries 2012)
- Source 2: CAC 1998, Christ Apostolic Church Constitution 1998 Lagos : CAC Printing press limited 1998
- Source 3: J. A Alokan (2010) Christ Apostolic Church @90(1918-2008) Ile-Ife: Timade

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1758-6623.1976.tb02440.x>
- Source 1 Description: The Christ Apostolic Church Its History, Beliefs and Organization
- Source 2 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/hts.v69i1.1333>
- Source 2 Description: The Origin , development and a brief appraisal of the doctrine of the baptism in the Holy Spirit in Christ Apostolic Church , Nigeria

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1758-6623.1976.tb02440.x>
- Source 1 Description: The Christ Apostolic Church it's history, beliefs and organization
- Source 2 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/hts.v69i1.1333>
- Source 2 Description: The origin, development and brief appraisal of the doctrine of the baptism in the Holy Spirit in Christ Apostolic Church, Nigeria
- Source 1 URL: <https://thekingsbible.com>
- Source 1 Description: KJV Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: CAC adherents do not live in isolation of their community, they have culture contact with the people. Within the community, people of different religious traditions and beliefs live together. In what exist on ground around the study area, there are situations where an individual who belongs to a particular religious group is still actively involved with persons of other religious traditions. Situations exist where parents of an individual who belongs to the religious group are of different faiths. Notwithstanding, they are still able to live under the same roof. There are Instances where spouses belong to different faith traditions. yet their differences in faith constitutes no hindrance to their peaceful co-existence. Among the Yoruba ethnic group where CAC as a religious group is prominent, It is not uncommon to see husband and wife belonging to different religious traditions. Each spouse will practice his or her religion without any fuss. They will live together not minding their differences on religious ground. While the husband may be a Muslim, the wife may choose to follow another religious tradition. like Christianity or African indigenous religious tradition It can as well be vice -versa

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: In some instances, the cultural contact is not neutral. There have been occasional occurrences of religious tension between religious groups in southern Nigeria while occurrences of religious intolerance have been more prominent in the northern part of the country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There have been occurrences of violent religious conflicts in northern Nigeria.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: To be a member or affiliated to the religious group, you must have passed through process of baptism and acceptance of the tenet of the group. The tenets include the following 1. The unity of the God head and the trinity of the person therein 2. The utter depravity of human nature, the necessity for repentance and the regeneration and the eternal doom of the finally impenitent 3. The virgin birth, sinless life, atoning death, triumphant resurrection, ascension and abiding intercession of our Lord Jesus Christ, his second coming, and millennial reign upon earth 4. Justification and sanctification of the believers through the finished work of Christ 5. The baptism of the Holy Spirit for the believers with signs following 6. The nine gifts of the Holy Spirit for the edification and comfort of the church which is the body of Christ 7. The sacraments of baptism by immersion and the Lord's supper 8. The divine inspiration and authority of the Holy Scriptures. 9. Church government by Apostles, Prophets, Evangelists,, Pastors, Church teachers, and Elders/Deacons 10. The obligatory nature of tithe and offerings 11. The possibility of falling from grace 12. Divine healing through obedience to the command of our Lord Jesus Christ and faith in His name and merits of His blood for all sicknesses, diseases, and infirmities 13. Faith in God, the Jehovah-jireh to supply all financial needs without going into debt or borrowing money on interest, to be contented with having food and raiment. Godliness with contentment is a great gain, and the love of money is the root of all evil

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: An individual can claim to be a member if his or her parent is a member or if he or she is

born in the religious group. However this does not necessarily qualify the individual the due right until he or she must have passed through the due process to be a full member. For instance until you are baptized after you must have attained a minimum of twelve years of age, you cannot partake in holy communion

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals can also choose to join or withdraw from the religious group. The religious group does not coerce anybody into joining or leaving the group. Though they have a way of influencing their members decision through preaching and persuasion. Evangelism is another way by which the membership of the religious group has risen over the years. This is a process of reaching out to none members through preaching and sharing their beliefs with them. Through this process people are maintained and retained in the religious group

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There is no caste system within the religious group. Every member has equal opportunity as long as they remain and maintain their statutory obligation within the religious group. It is very much possible to grow from being just a member to becoming one of the leaders in the religious group. Membership is therefore open to all classes whether rich or the poor

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Membership is not assigned at any specific age as one can become a member at any stage of life; either as an adolescent, young adult, adult or at old age. This all depends on personal choice and individual situation. On another note, membership can be assigned through birth especially if one's parents are members of the group or if an individual is born in the group. However one can only attain full membership after sacrament of water baptism. At infant, the full decision to be a member can be decided by the parent. The young ones are usually taught in the church children class where they will be made to learn about the beliefs and practices of the group. They will be orientated and encouraged to serve God. At age twelve they would be given opportunity to partake in baptism for them to become full member. Some may decide to postpone until when they are ready for it in later years. After the water baptism full members are allowed to partake in Holy communion.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Gender is not a criterion for becoming a member of the religious group. As long as one is willing to follow their beliefs and practices, becoming a member and attaining leadership position will never be an issue.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: One can attain full membership through baptism, commitment to the teaching of the church and actively participating in the programme of the church. Every full member is expected to follow the tenets of the church

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group anchors their faith on the bible.. The motto of the church is "One fold, one Shepherd". They also have a vision statement "Soul winning and spiritual re-awakening of the world " The mission statement of the church is " Leading people into the knowledge of God through an in-depth study of the word of God" Both the vision statement and mission are pointers in the direction of proselyting and recruitment into the group. This is done through various methods. The method employed can be in form of mass mobilization of the adherents to go out and evangelize. It can also be through one on one evangelization. . The members usually go out in large numbers or on individual basis to evangelize non members. Sometimes it can be in the early hours of the morning around 5:00am - 6:00am (morning cry). Through preaching, non members often accept the accept Christ. They attend the church teaching programmes and are brought into the church. They are taught about the group and at an appropriate time they are baptized to become full members

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Political affiliation is optional as individual can decide on which political party to follow. The church has no favourite political party or special affinity with any party.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of apostasy in the religious group is not when one leaves the religious group but when an individual decide not to follow Christian faith. An apostate is never punished or prosecuted, rather they pray for them hoping they may return back to the faith

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 5000000

Notes: The official population of the group was put at five million members. This was the official population as indicated in the review constitution of the year 1998 which was published by the church. Considering the expansion and the development that the church has experienced during the last 26 years the population could have increase tremendously. However another membership census of the church is due this year. <https://cacfc.org.uk/cac-history/>

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2.5

Notes: The population of Nigeria is estimated to be around two hundred million now (200,000000). The estimated population of the group is around 5 million members

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Nigeria is a secular state by her constitution but in practice Christianity and Islam are the major religious tradition.. Even at that, some of the religious adherent of these traditions still hold on to their African religious tradition. Hence an individual who claim to be a Christian can still be found observing his African religious practices as his or her identity is linked to it.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: At apex of the leadership in CAC the President is in number one position and he is followed by the General Superintendent and by the General Evangelist. These leaders are called the three principal officers. The President is the number one person in the group. He is the ceremonial and executive leader. The General Superintendent is the head pastor of all other Pastors in the religious group. However, the General Evangelist is the prophet and seer who is in charge of running the evangelism arm of the church. Other important leaders at the apex are the General Secretary, Finance director and Mission director. These leaders are saddled with the responsibility of providing spiritual guidance and administartive leadership for the church

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the size of the local community, the church may have a single leader or a number of them. However, there is usually one of the leaders who is saddled with the overall leadership of the church where there are two or more leaders of an assembly.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: There is a hierarchy among leaders of multiple religious communities in the group. Churches in the group are organised in circuits/district such that there is a District Superintendent who administers a number of local assemblies in their locality.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: Though the leaders are seen as humans, they are often held as possessing supernatural powers bestowed on them by the supreme being.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

- ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
- ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
- ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The group prays each time they desire to choose a new leader. They believe firmly in the powers of prayers in making the right choice of leaders.
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - No
 - Notes: Followers do not often charge their leaders with this form of accusation but they believe that as humans, their leaders are not infallible.
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In some instances, some aggrieved leaders within the group may charge the leadership of the group with the allegation of fallibility.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the only scripture that the religious group believes. In the early days of the group, the reading of psalm from the bible for prayer was very common. Today, the church has grown beyond just reading of psalm for prayer, they are now versatile in exegeting the whole of the biblical texts.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The bible in its current form is written but it was not sent down in written form. It is a revealed scripture

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Bible is the scripture of the religious group.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: The scripture was inspired by God

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture is based on inspiration derived from the high God. It is an inspired writing. 2Tim 3:16 "All scripture is given by inspiration of God, and is profitable for doctrine, for reproof, for correction, for instruction in righteousness"

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: They can't be altered

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The scripture is already available in various languages. Of course, there are theological schools available for those who want to be specialists in the interpretation of biblical texts.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The bible is canonized

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: There are no specific monuments in the CAC as a religious group; notwithstanding the church has specific spaces considered as sacred space where large numbers of adherents meet for religious purposes and for conferences. There is a place called Ikeji Arakeji in Osun State, Nigeria. Ikeji Arakeji was the place where Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola had an encounter with the divine. It all happened in the year 1928 along Ilesa Igbara Oke road. Babalola had been working with a steamroller on the road when the engine suddenly stopped without any mechanical fault. He tried to make the engine work

again but all his efforts proved abortive. Babalola however was able to push the steamroller by his sole effort to the side of the road mysteriously. It was after this that he heard a voice which sounded like many waters . The voice called his name three times and instructed him to heed divine call to be a preacher and messenger of God. The voice which spoke to him assured him of divine protection and guidance.. The voice used palm leaves which Babalola had struck down while attempting to fix the steamroller as a parable for him. One part of the palm leaves was fresh, one was half fresh and the other was dried. The palm leaves were used as a symbolic representation of the reward awaiting those who will accept his message and the extent they accept it. The fresh one represents those who will fully accept his message, it indicates that their life will be fresh.. The half dried is for those who will accept his message partially; and the dried are for those who will reject his message.. Today the site where the encounter took place has become a sacred space where people visit for spiritual revival and renewal. The camp ground of the church is located in the town. The site also hosts the church university known as Joseph Ayo Babalola University (JABU).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: CAC as a religious group does not support building of monument for her heroes . However there are religious spaces where fathers of faith in CAC had trod which though are not monuments but are considered as special religious spaces for spiritual awakening. The first General Evangelist of the church Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola had special mountains where he had prayed and got empowered. such special places like mountains are given special recognition by many adherents. These spaces serve as places where people go for prayer.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: The leadership frowns at such practices yet it cannot be totally denied among the followers

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The CAC believes in the distinctiveness of the human spirit from the human body. The celestial body (spirit world) is different from the physical world inhabited by the human body. This celestial body is different from the mortal body. This is centered on the biblical teaching found in 1 Corinthians 15:40 "There are also celestial bodies, and bodies terrestrial; but the glory of the celestial is one and the glory of the terrestrial is another". It is believed that the earthly body cannot inherit the spirit world. They are distinct and separated from each other. The celestial body is the spirit body and it is incorruptible and immortal whereas terrestrial body is corruptible and mortal 1Corinthians 15:53. This of course can be linked to the faith of the group about life hereafter. The third tenet of the church emphasises the virgin birth, sinless life, atoning death, triumphant resurrection, ascension, and abiding intercession of our Lord Jesus Christ, his second coming and millennial reign upon the earth.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes in life hereafter. Death is not the end of life but transition to a better and glorious plane of existence. The spirit which exists in a man transcends the terrestrial world. Through the spirit, connection with God is possible because God is conceived as a spirit. After death the spirit goes back to God and gives account of his sojourn while in the terrestrial body.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes in life after death. Life now is conceived as a phase and preparatory ground to a life hereafter. There are two conceptions about life hereafter; one is eternal life in bliss and glory; and the second is eternal punishment of severe torture and pain. This is according to biblical teaching in Matthew 25:46. "And these shall go away into everlasting punishment but the righteous into eternal life" Members are encouraged to live moderately, show love to others, and exhibit piety so as not to lose their reward and life in eternity. Life in eternity is also the same as life in paradise where everything will be perfect. Hell is a place of eternal torment and separation from God.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Re-incarnation is not part of the belief system of CAC, however there are individuals who hold on to such belief system due to their cultural background. The Yoruba traditional belief and similar worldview of re-incarnation are not supported by CAC tenet. On the contrary, there are members of this religious group whose names suggest belief in re-incarnation. Names like Babatunde meaning "Father has returned," Yewande: Mother has come back to us. and many related names like that. This is a reflection of such belief system among the adherent. However the church frowns at such practices. The position of the church is premised on Hebrew 9:27 "As it is appointed unto men once to die and after this the judgement".

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Whenever an adherent of the faith dies, the family of the deceased decide on the funeral rite in consultation with the leaders of the church.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The group does not have such practices.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not present.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: When an adherent of the faith dies, the burial rites are usually done formally. Depending on the family and the local assembly where the individual involved had lived. In some towns and cities, the religious group (CAC) has cemeteries where members who died may be buried. This of course depends on the arrangement with the family.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: Building of cenotaphs for deceased members of the group is not a practice associated with the group.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: It is allowed

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Burying loved ones in a family tomb is never an issue with the leadership of the religious group. The concern in most cases is on the likely outcome of the practice. This is because such practice may aid the practice of ancestor worship where the living members of the family who are members of the church may be tempted or compelled to pay obeisance or perform traditional rites to the dead. Ancestor worship had long be a part of religious practices among Africans. The church however frowns at turning burial tombs to a religious entity where the family members will go and offer prayers to the dead.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the availability of space within the area where they intend to bury the dead. There are those who may decide to bury their dead beneath the house or areas used for normal domestic activities. It all depends on the family and the discretion of the church officials.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Mausoleum

Notes: Mausoleum is another form of burial site built for the influential individual or the rich who can afford it, Mausoleum is usually a stately built structure with distinct architectural design that house the tomb of an individual who had led an influential life. There are few leaders among the leaders of the church who have had mausoleum built for them. Prominent is Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola Mausoleum.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: He is not fused with earthly monarch rather the earthly king is his subject

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: He is related only to the just and the right living human

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: He is loyal only to the right standing individual

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Faithful to the faithful

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: He is unrestricted

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is unrestricted everywhere

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

–Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: He is an all knowing God

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: He is an all knowing God. The creator of the universe

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Though he controls all, he still allow human to determine and dictate the direction he (human) wants to take

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: He is conceived as Almighty

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: He is considered good

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: He will do to you according to individual work before him. He is a God that rewards according to individual's deed

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God hunger is that all should worship him; however he does not force his will on human. He grants freewill for human to decide on what to do.

Human are allowed to choose freely whether to serve him or not

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: To worship other god is considered an offence. The only supernatural to worship or serve is the high God who sits in heaven. His hunger is that all must acknowledge him as all in all and worship only him

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Love

Notes: He is considered as a loving father who cares for all his children and subjects

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Divination is considered abnormal though few adherents may be tacitly getting involved in such

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Both religious specialist and non religious specialist are believed to be capable of receiving trance or dream from God

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

–Yes [specify]: High God can as well communicate to his subject through the reading and teaching of the sacred text. Anytime when the sacred text is opened and read, there is belief that High God himself is the one speaking to his subject

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Some adherents can claim they feel the presence of the supernatural but in reality they can't be seen

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally

visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have knowledge of past, present and future events in the physical and spiritual worlds.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: It is believe among the adherents that if one is faithful and committed one can be blessed through the supernatural

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: They can punish using delegated authority given to them by the supernatural being.

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They exhibit this only when the nature of the duty being undertaken under the instruction of the supreme being demands this. For example when they are under instruction to punish an individual or a nation for gross disobedience to divine command

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Their hunger is not one for food or other inordinate desires. They possess hunger to fulfil divine commands.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They are loving, helpful and always interested in fulfilling their divine mandate from the supreme being.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess a variety of supernatural being, however they acknowledge the presence of other divine beings

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes that whenever they gather for religious activities, God is present and he is there to oversee all of their activities. God is considered supernatural and cannot be explained by natural, physical or material laws. More so there is belief that God can send his angel to do such things that defy natural law. These are called miracles or acts of the supernatural.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents believe anytime they gather for religious rituals i.e. prayer, worship, singing etc that God is ever present with them.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme God is considered to be all powerful and good. His attributes can be found in man. He can speak and hear, you can talk back to Him, He can send messages through various unusual ways, He can relate, protect, guide and direct human beings. The Yoruba people have various ways of addressing this supreme high God i.e Olowogbogboro, Eleti lu kara bi ajere, Onikan gbe ra re nija etc.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: He is considered as God of heaven and earth

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: His abode is above yet he is everywhere

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: He is called the king or Kabiyesi or Kabio-osi. meaning unquestionable.. Kabiyesi/ Kabiesi is an appellation for an earthly Yoruba king. He is believed to be supreme and higher than the earthly king

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: To some degree, an absolute monarch can be likened to God who is held as superior to everyone else. He rules in the affairs of humans.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: He is father to all, the rich, the poor and the powerful

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: He is related to all and loyal to those who are loyal to him

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme God is considered extremely good in all of his dealings with his subjects. Even in odd and unfavorable situation he is considered good.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omniscient, omnipotent.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: He is believed to be the creator of the world. He has absolute knowledge of the world..

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Supreme God's knowledge is absolute as he knows even the end from beginning. He knows everything., he is unrestricted God

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Supreme God is considered to be a universal God. He is not restricted by space, time and season. The Yoruba call him Olodumare. Within the sample area especially in southwest Nigeria, there are church cathedrals built long ago with inscriptions on the altar where the priest usually sit. These inscriptions are written in Yoruba, Mimo, Mimo, Momo, Oluwa Olorun Olodumare meaning Holy, Holy, Holy, Lord God Almighty

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is believed to operate everywhere. There is the belief among the adherents that every secret can be revealed by him through prophecy, trance, dream and other supernatural means

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is an Almighty and all knowing God. He is unrestricted in knowledge. There are adherents of the faith in many nations of the world today. The church has branches in Europe; UK, France, Italy etc. It also has branches in USA and Canada. He is not restricted but present every where

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Nothing can hide from his presence. Even in darkness he sees

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Wherever you stay or go, the Supreme God can see you there. Either in the light or in the darkness. He is believed to be present. even in the dark corners of the home he is there.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God is the discerner of the human heart. He knows the thoughts of the heart of human beings and can predict the outcome even before it happens..

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: He can predict what you will do and what you will not do

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme God is an all knowing God. He can see the future from now and the likely choice individuals will make. This is why prophecy is believed by many adherents of the faith. Many consult prophets for the sake of getting direction. Some among the adherent will rather obey what the prophet says than what the Pastor says. There is this belief among them that the prophet will hear directly from God but the Pastor will only use the scripture to guide them

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: As the creator of everything. He knows every part and everything about the world

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong belief that the Supreme God rewards. He rewards every service done by the adherents on his behalf whether good or bad. There is emphasis on showing love and care for others, winning soul by preaching and praying for others. The adherents believe there is a reward for any of the good

deed done for others. There are rewards for those who are faithful and walk in obedience to God's laws

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: To the adherents of the faith, God is seen as a just God who can either reward you for good or punish you for evil. For every good you do, expect the reward and for every evil expect a reward as well. The adherents can spend hours or even days in prayer asking God to act in a way especially for justice. God is believed to be a just God who will give according to each person's way. He deals with the wicked in his own time

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: He is considered as the Almighty, his will is considered as the supreme

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: when He is pleased with you, he will favour you and if otherwise you are in for his trouble

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The hunger of God is to save humanity from himself and from evil. He wants everyone to love him and also love their neighbor so as to reign with him. This is captured by the third tenet of the church " the virgin birth, sinless life, atoning death, triumphant resurrection, ascension and abiding intercession of our Lord Jesus Christ, his second coming and millennial reign upon earth"

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The supreme high God detest that. He is a jealous God and does not want any other being to be worshiped except him. His command is to be obeyed and only him alone should be worshipped.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

–Yes [specify]: He is an all knowing God

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: They are believed to be celestial in form

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: This is left to the perception of the worshipper who believed in the supernatural presence when they gather to observe their religious rite

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They are believed to have knowledge about humans. This includes even the knowledge that humans don't have about themselves and other phenomena in the physical and spiritual worlds.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: They can tell of other regions as well

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: They can foretell and forthtell

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: They are considered as supernatural, they possess the ability to know what you did

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: To a certain degree they can see the motive behind your action

Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: They are familiar with your life. they can easily predict you

Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They have the understanding of what lies in the future and you are likely to do

Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: have they being, supernatural are they Yes are Since

– Yes [specify]: have they being, supernatural are they Yes are Since

Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: They can support and influence those who work in line with their instruction

These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This can happen when you fail to abide by their instruction

These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: These supernatural may exhibit both positive and negative emotion. This is because they want to control human

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Their hunger is to control human

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: To control human

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: They don't possess supernatural beings but they acknowledge their existence

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes they are being protected, guided and directed from above. This belief is premised on the biblical promises that he will charge his angel to keep you in all your ways (Psalm 91:11). It is also believed that the high God does not sleep nor slumber so he keeps all his subject and protect them from evil (Psalm121:4). (2Chro16:9), "For the eyes of the Lord run to and fro throughout the whole earth, to shew himself strong in the behalf of them whose heart is perfect toward him.". The religious group believed they are under the care of the high God. They also accept the fact that they will account for their deed as they are being monitored from abode

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes that every human action has corresponding reward in this life and life after. Biblical passages like Roman 14:12 says "so then every one of us shall give account of himself to God"

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Among the adherents, certain actions are considered as taboo and could attract the anger of God. Members are warned not to thread the part of what is forbidden. CAC as a large

church has her congregation spread across many regions in Nigeria, therefore the local authority and the leadership of each congregation exercise a certain level of autonomy. The way taboos are observed or conceived therefore varies. In most cases, local leadership directs and guides the action of their congregation on their sacred spaces and sacred objects. Members are encouraged to follow the dictate guiding sacred space, sacred object and the leading of Holy Spirit.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: There is no specific taboo placed on any kind of food by the authority of the church. However food offered to idol, unsafe for human consumption, and that can affect the belief of others within the religious group are forbidden. At local level different congregation can as well dictate what to eat or not especially if the members are engaging in fasting and prayer at a specific time. When engaging in fasting and prayer restriction for a specific time can be placed on what to eat. Depending on the kind of fasting, it can be an absolute fasting where restriction will be placed on any kind of food for the period of time when engaging in spiritual exercise, or dry fasting when one abstain from food and water for a specific period of days or white fasting when certain food cannot be used to break the fasting in the evening.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The spaces considered as sacred spaces vary from one location to another. The commonest sacred space for the adherents is the church building where believers meet for religious purposes. Generally the church building will have a space specially reserved for the minister. The space reserved is usually restricted for the ministers alone. No one is allowed to come in except with the expressed permission of the minister or church leader in charge. The space is considered as sacred and the most holy of all the church building. Other prominent sacred space is the prayer mountain where people go for spiritual rearmament and exercise. The most common restriction to the prayer mountain is the removing of footwear before climbing up to certain area of the mountain. There are laws that forbid using footwear to certain parts of the mountain. The local authority managing such spaces like prayer mountain and other sacred spaces also decide the extend by which an individual who wants to access the space can go.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: CAC as a religious group believes that any objects separated for the use of the church is sacred and should be used for the purpose only. Prominent of all sacred object is the hand bell. During the early days of the church, Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola one of the early fathers of the church had instructed that bell should always be rung before the start of any service as it will not only call people's attention that the service has started but also has a covenant to drive away evil forces within the vicinity. This has become the practices among CAC members that bell will be rung before the service start. There are many other sacred objects like holy communion vase, cup, drum, etc. Every object separated for the use of church are sacred .

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The supernatural God cares for his subjects by answering their prayers and keeping them safe. He is loving, protecting and always providing for their needs

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: CAC believes that the high God is against killing. They hold on to the concept of sanctity of every life. The church has no room or teaching that permits murder of any form. The great high God they worship forbid murder in totality

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is a grave offence. Biblical injunction says "Thou shall not kill" (Exo 20:13)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: In the sacred text the bible, the church believes that adultery is against the will of God. It is only those who are married that are expected to engage in sex. Adultery is seen as a sin. Also sexual relationship among sibling or those who are related is considered as taboo and perversion of sexuality.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: CAC believes that every other form of sexual practices outside marriage is against the law of God. They hold jealously the biblical injunction of Gen 2:24 "Therefore shall a man leave his father and mother , and shall cleave unto his wife; and they shall be one flesh"

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Every member is expected to be faithful in every aspect of their lives. God demands that they should be holy and truthful in all they do.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The belief of the group is that God does not encourage oath taking but when it is done, it should be honour

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The teaching of CAC is totally against laziness by members in any form. The church encourages hard-work, diligence and faithfulness as an antidote to poverty. Biblical injunction in (Proverb 6:6-11) says "Go to the ant, thou sluggard; consider her way, and be wise" Paul's admonition in (2Thess3:10) is practical on the need to work "For even when we were with you, this we commanded you, that if any would not work, neither should he eat"

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is conceived as a form of spiritual manipulation among the believers. It is condemned and legislated against. It is considered as one of the works of the flesh. It is against the teaching of the religious group. If any member is found to be involved, he/she is immediately sanctioned and excommunicated as a member of the group

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: God is not against self defense even though he is not interested in fighting. He is a God of peace but in situation where living in peace is problematic, non-lethal fighting to demoralise the enemy is accepted until when peace reigns

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches faith in God. God wants all who will serve him to do so in faith. Therefore anyone who shirks responsibility can not please God. Christian are to live by faith. and not to avoid responsibility

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: The church frowns at any form of dis-respectfulness. Elders are to be respected and treated as fathers and mothers. Even the young are to be treated as sibling. This is part of the church tradition. the aged are respected

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Anything a man does to his/her fellow human to cheat him/her is a crime. Cheating on property is a crime

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Every believer is expected to worship God appropriately. There are kind of worship that are considered acceptable and the one unacceptable before God. For any ritual observance to be acceptable to God, there must be sincerity of heart, there must be obedience to God, the individual concern must show love and compassion for others and must worship God in truth and spirit.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: The church has a vision statement which is "soul winning and spiritual re-awakening of the world". It also has a mission statement which states " leading people into the knowledge of God through an in depth study of the word of God, prevailing prayer, and spiritual worship". The church believes in conversion and has a missionary department and evangelical department who are saddled with the responsibility to reach out to people of other faith with the purpose of converting them to the faith. Beyond this, every member is expected to be a soul-winner

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The CAC believes that everyone should be given his/her dues. Cheating and owing someone is a crime against God and humanity. The high God commands that everyone should be treated fairly. Biblical injunction in (Lev. 19:13) states that you should not defraud your neighbour and (James 5:4) says that the wages of the people you hire must be paid as their cries has reached up to God

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Personal hygiene is very paramount. There are references about cleanliness and hygiene in both old testament and new testament(Lev.11-15). As indicated in the Holy scripture (1Cor 6:19-20)every believers body is the temple of the Holy spirit and God cannot dwell in dirt or in an unkept place. Therefore, every believer is expected to care for his/her hygiene. Failure to care for personal hygiene can lead to ailment and promote all forms of sicknesses and diseases.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: CAC believes that God cares for all of his subject by showing them love, providing for their needs, protecting them from all evil and guiding them right in all that they do

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: If this is yes such a claim may not be instant or proven scientifically.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: The members of the religious group may answer in affirmative claiming they have been rewarded by God. Many of such claims cannot be scientifically proven

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group based her eschatological belief on biblical doctrine. They believe in the rapture , second coming and millennium reign of Christ on earth

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The whereabouts of the Messiah is known. He is said to be in heaven where he preparing an eternal resting place for those who belief in him. However, his time of return is not known. He said of himself that he will come at a time that no man expects.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: He made a first coming and is scheduled to return a second time.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: He came to redeem man back unto God and to bring an end to the agelong separation of man from God.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: They need to preach the gospel to others all over the world to bring many to the saving knowledge of their messiah.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The group beliefs that eschaton will bring about divine reign and God's theocratic government on the world.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: The new religious system the group beliefs will be established is that already practiced in heaven where God is the all in all. No other desire or opposing government will be allowed in this new reign on earth.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only those who truly practice the will and command of the supreme being will survive the eschaton.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are prescription on what members are expected to do in the society. They are expected to be law abiding, show love to people and be their brother's keeper. These norms are for self preservation.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: In some instances the norms are specifically meant to keep the sanity of the group and prevent bad behavior

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: The norms in most cases are for self preservation

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: For the religious group it's about them living exemplary life

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: They are for the adherents especially the priest to keep the sanctity of their religion

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

Notes: In most cases they don't have any direct connection with the metaphysical being

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within contemporary world

Notes: They are norms expected to be observed by individuals to guarantee human existence

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: Emphasis is on inner beauty or the human character above the physical beauty alone.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The group also teaches forbearance, mercy, devotion, smartness in conducting oneself and industry.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy is an option within the religious group no one is commanded to be a celibate. In most cases to be ordained as a Pastor or appointed as an Elder or Deacon/ness marriage is one of the pre requisite. It is only on rare occasion that a pastor will be unmarried in the religious group.. Celibacy is not a practice in the religious group

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Sexual purity is expected from the members.. Sexual activity without being married is considered as sin and frowned at by the group. When an unmarried member got involved in sexual act and is known to the leaders it is regarded as fornication and biblical teaching will be used to sanction such an individual. However, sexual act between spouse is never considered in negative light. As long as the partner remain faithful to themselves, sexual activity is never against the norms

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is alien to the group

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting and prayer is a normal practice of the group. Three days, seven days and marathon prayer and fasting are common in the group. The early fathers of the faith in the religious group were called Aladura "Praying persons". Fasting to them are fundamental to serving the Lord. There were series of stories on the exploit made through fasting and prayer of . Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola. At his first divine encounter, while driving a steam roller along ilesa Igbara oke road. He was asked to pray and fast. Fasting and prayer is very important to the group. There is a popular saying among the adherents that "A prayerless life is a powerless life"

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– No

Notes: Except food offer for sacrifice, idol or food from an unknown origin. Every Food is good and clean after it must have been prayed to or sanctified

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: This is not part of the practices of the group

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Such is never part of their practices

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: The faith of the members in the religious group is solely based in Jesus Christ who they believed has paid the supreme sacrifice and no other sacrifice is expected from anybody again. The members also believed in their fathers of faith like Joseph Ayo Babalola and others. No adult sacrifice is needed

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Such is unknown in the religious group

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Suicide is considered as sin against God

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Even though the group don't demand for the sacrifice of her members building or property. Notwithstanding anyone who sell valuables or property for the sake of the religious group acknowledged

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Regular programs are organized like Bible study, revival program, tarrying meeting for the Holy spirit. All these involve sacrifice of time by the adherent

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: No physical risk is involved in practices of their religious rites

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the religious group are expected to be tolerant and law abiding citizen in the community where they live

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Members are always encouraged to build their spiritual capacity. For this to be done, individual must engage in private spiritual exercise. Household ritual like morning prayer and evening prayer before bedtime. Reading of bible, giving offering, prayer and fasting are among the commonest ritual among the religious group

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 1

Notes: This depends on the kind of program that the religious group organized. If it were to be mountain program, There could be hourly prayer, or that of three hour interval or the one that involve specific hour of the day like 6:00am, 9:00am, 12:00noon, 3:00pm and 6:00pm.. It all depend on the location and purpose of such prayer

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: It ranges from a hundred to thousands of people. The religious group could organize a large scale ritual that the minimum number can be like one thousand and to several thousands

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 22

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The most senior of the priest ensure orderliness and strict adherence to the laid down rules of their ritual

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Even though they have those in supervisory capacity sometimes they only ensure those below them are operating within the practices of their religious group. They are usually not too strict when discharging their religious function

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Such is considered as odd

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Though there is no rigid laid down rules for such, circumcision is permitted for baby boys but tattoos or scarifications are not fashionable among them.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The group consider members as brothers and sister

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: Fictive kinship is not uncommon. During the early church days, christian men were called brothers and christian women were called sisters. This still applies today among some denominations. It also applies among some congregation of CAC

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: This religious group known as CAC has different level of operation. They are organized and name as assembly, district, Zone, District coordinating council and Region. The assembly is the least of all the leadership cadre and is headed by a pastor who operate within an area where the church is located. Next in command is the District Superintendent Pastor who supervises more than one assembly within an area. Zone is headed by a senior Pastor who oversees more than one districts and district coordinating council Pastor have many districts to oversee than that of zonal Pastor.. Next is the Regional leadership. This is under the leadership of a Pastor called Regional Superintendent.. A pastor who occupies such a position have a large areas which can comprise more than one state of the federation to lead.. All the district coordinating and zonal pastors are directly under him. Superior to the Regional Pastor is the Presidency where all the executive power emanate. At the Presidency, the President of the mission is number one. This is followed by the General Superintendent and the third is the General Evangelist. These three are called the Principal officers of the church. Also in the presidency are the General Secretary, the Finance Director and Mission Director.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: CAC as a religious group does support humanitarian services to her members and non members. Within her organization provisions are made for the less privilege and the needy. However, a large scale institutionalized relief program for famine relief rarely happens. In cases when there is need for famine relief in an area, assembly of worshipper at local level are in most cases are saddled with such responsibilities. Sometimes welfare package are sent through representatives of the leaders to

support the needy

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Famine in most cases is not so much prevalent in some areas in Nigeria. This does not imply that there are no poor or needy who need relief materials. In most cases when relief materials are sent or provided it is usually done through the religious group members at the local level to their members and not through any institution(s) provided by the government

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: As at today, a concrete institutionalized poverty relief program from the religious group is not fully operational. Though the religious group provide poverty alleviation relief to people. The effort is not fully institutionalized.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Provision of poverty relief program outside of this religious group rarely happen. At the assembly level of the church, individual influential member can sometimes be seen supporting the poor or providing relief material for the needy. The relief materials for the poor and the needy are mostly source within with few exception

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The religious group as an institution does not operate such a care facility as at present. Yet it is not an offense for individual or any member to operate such if the law of the land support the action. There are members of the religious group who operate care facilities and other NGO

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The church does not have any approved Centre for the elderly or the infirm. Neither is the church against the practices. However, the church believes that the family should be responsible to cater for their aged ones. In situation when family members are not available the church at the local level has always provided a local arrangement at the assembly level to cater for such situation. However, there is no institutionalized provision to cater for the elderly generally. it is rather done base on the need and among the local members

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The members are encouraged to have formal education. The first primary school of the church was opened in the year 1934, in Efon Alaaye in Ekiti State. This was followed by opening of several others schools to cater for the children of adherents who were denied admission into mission schools when the church started. and was under persecution from the mission church. In the year 2006, the church opened a university named after Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola. The Private university is known today as Joseph Ayo Babalola University. (JABU). It is one of the leading private university in Nigeria. It is located in Ikeji Arakeji where Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola had encounter with the divine and commissioned into the ministry. Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola international miracle centre is also located in Ikeji Arakeji. The venue usually play host to most of the camp program, conferences and various large gathering of the church.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Formal education is opened to all and sundry among the adherents. The religious education is not only open to religious professional, it is also accessible to non religious professionals as well. Early in the history of the church, there were effort to train the church workers. In the year 1952, Bible training college was started at Ede. The school commence training for Catechists. By the year 1954, the college was moved to Erio Ekiti. In the year 1957 the college was moved again to Efon -Alaaye where Mrs.A.O. Pierce served as the Principal. Year 1968 was another year as the school was moved to Akure and remained there till 1973. Mrs. Pierce was assigned to another arm of the ministry. It is of note to state that in the year 1963, pastoral training led to the founding of Christ Apostolic Church Pastoral training institute. By the year 1979, the church authority fused all existing training colleges together to begin Christ Apostolic Church theological Seminary Ile-Ife. The school was headed by Pastor Busuyi Faloye and he was replaced by Pastor J.O. AKintola . The current provost of the seminary as at 2023 is Professor C,O, Oshun. CAC opened her seminary to both religious professional and non professional . .

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The training school is opened to both male and female at the main campus of the seminary. However, there are satellite campuses that train only one gender, Babajide school of prophet and Evangelist is not opened to both gender. The school of Prophet and Evangelist is male only. Also there is another satellite campus in Ede, this campus is female only. Female ministers are taught and trained in the campus

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Member are encouraged to get educated and attend any institution of their choice. The is no compulsion on the school to attend in as much the school is approved by the government.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: As much as the leaders of the religious group are powerful so also are the adherent powerful. The Elders operate at the assembly level yet they are very powerful and have a way of influencing what happen at every level of the church. They are have a way of shaping the direction of the church through the support, counsel and expertise when use for the benefit of the religious group. Elders are not transferable but the Pastors are, through this they are able to shape the direction of which the church should go. They can sometimes influence or help to shape the direction or decision of the church leaders when they enter into dialogue with the church leaders. They have ways of interfering and getting involved in the bureaucracy of the church

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the adherents are technocrat who hold public offices. They are men and women of different social strata.. Entrepreneur, business men and women, artisans, Engineer, Doctor, etc. There are many professionals who are members Even there are politician among the adherent. Therefore, they interact with others institutional bureaucracies

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Such is not common in the religious group

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no food storage provided by the religious group or by the government

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: None of such is provided by the religious group. However in some areas where access to water is hard. If the religious group has her branch around the area, pipe borne water may be provided for the people residing around the area by the religious group

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: In part of Africa where this religious institution thrives water resources are mainly provided by individual as the one provided by the government is not wide spread

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Except within their space such as camp ground

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the location However transportation infrastructure are provided by the government in most cases

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The tenth tenet of the church is the obligatory nature of tithes and offerings. Every member is expected to pay tithe and offering . It is without exemption. Tithe is the tenth percent of individual income, this is claimed to belong to God. The adherents are taught the importance of tithe and how it was commanded to be paid by God.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government accept tax from the citizen and every member of the group, as a citizen pays tax

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The group relies on the public police even though they have a Royal shepherd which is a non arm carrying civil security organ within their religious group. The Royal Shepherd is an arm of the religious group department that assist in providing guide and internal security among the members especially when holding a large religious program within the group.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents rely solely on police force for their security Any other security apart from.the police force is secondary

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: There is no such thing expect if member of the religious group who is a government lawyer attain the height through government appointment

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Anytime there are cases in court, members of judiciary are contacted for their services

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: It is very rare except for the ordained members of the group

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Such a thing is not common

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the formal code within the group are biblically derived

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are to adhere to the law of the land where they reside in as much it does not restrict them from practicing their religious belief

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: They solely rely on the military provided by the government

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are members of the group who are military officer

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by

an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group does not have her own military. They are protected or guarded under the official military of the state

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Though a large number of her members are people of Yoruba ethnic group. Their languages are both English & Yoruba. People of other ethnic within Nigeria who belong to the same religious group do speak their native languages

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and Yoruba Languages

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and Yoruba languages

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Their calendar follows a Gregorian calendar from January to December. The yearly events of the religious group are spelt out in the church annual calendar. The group calendar usually takes cognizance of the government calendar. The commonest events of the religious group are as follows: 1. CACTS Old students Annual Conference 2. National Sunday school Examination 3. Sunday School Day 4. Annual Sunday School Rally 5. Midwives' Conference 6. Minister's Wives' Conference 7. Elders' Conference (at DCC/Zonal levels) 8. Children Workers' Seminar 9. Publicity Week/ Conference 10. Music Ministers' Conference 11. CAC Good women Association's Annual Conference 12. CAC Youth Conference 13. Annual Pastors' Conference 14. Evangelists, Prophets and Church Planters' Conference 15. Royal Shepherd Conference 16. Annual General Council Meeting These are the usual calendar of the religious group in a year.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The religious group has her own calendar. The calendar takes into cognizance the official

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

– No

Notes: There is no institutionalized provision of food for the adherents of the group. Most of the assembly that provide food tend to do so within their means. Provision of food is made for the less privilege and the needy mostly during festive period or holiday

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: CAC as a religious group does not usually provide food for her adherents neither does she have food provision from any institution. Within every assembly notwithstanding provisions are made for members who are indigent and are in need of help. Also during celebration or festive period, there are assemblies (local churches) in some areas who walk the part of sharing of food or visiting the motherless babies homes, prisons and homes of the needy to support them in whatever way they desire. However, there is no institutionalized provision or procedure for this through the highest governing body of the religious group. Provision or sharing of food varies from one location to another. There are assemblies who hardly pursue a task of sharing food.